

Editorial policy setting

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15 March 202

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The audience of the research organisation.

This editorial board making to the audience of the scientific fictions in the philosophy of alchemy and the modern chemistry to be defined as the amazing magical science that applied to all types of the sciences and classified it. Where the editor make up for the audience of the jordanian believe by the mysterious, adventure, romance, and magical behaviours and principal from the arabian roots and strong ideal thinking. As it go to the audience hope in chemistry yo be the active scientists.

The goals of contents

The goals are to create and build the hands of Jordan as the king Abdullah II believe and want to be found effectivelly by the seven discussion paper and especially the seventh paper, and to improve our patient in the scientific and amazing believings in the sciences especially chemistry. As the editorial processing make to be done for my home laboratory in chemistry named by Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory. As I believe with my team in the editing the factors that take the highest spaces in the editing which are the analysing and ctering of the research where it will be investigated by the using of the quantitative approaches of the research, then the Frameworks for content optimization where the studies will be respect after the theoritical analysis to make the adventures in it in the experimental details where the experimental details more important than the theoritical framework but it nessary to detecting the accuracy of the experiments more than the using of the proposals. After that the How to plan and structure content marketing teams by the combination of the team rules, the skills, the arts and sciences, and the strategies of the planings, then use the importance of content briefs & how to create them where it is very important in the posters and presentations ppt formates that also take the DOI identifier, after that the rules of the related topics that help them do their jobs better, where it is very important as the determinations of the adventures and the mysterious studies.

Explain of preferred content

The content that preferred in the editorial process are the authority content and the affinity content, where it must be go legally to the authors and the team of the author legally by registered their names, then the rights will be given for them at the same level without the distinguish that only who distinguished is the authors. And the affinity must be in the Arabia language for the thesis and the dissertations of the Alelaimat

Chemistry Laboratory and only the papers will be in the English language or the Arabia language. Where the author build all of the study and the team of he will be as the guiding team for some conditions go to make them the team of the major researcher, and the language is to improve the hardest rules of the Arabia language in Jordan letter by this patients of Jordan and the king Abdullah II.

Explain what do not cover

The editorial process of the Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory organization is only for the organization products to pre-review it, where it have some rules can not found in other journals, the editing only covered the organization products and the organization thesis and dissertations in the arabian language and the requirements for the studies in it. In the editing information the fields that can not be covered are the competitors where they can not be able to determined, the sensitive topics also can not be determined in the study, as the irrelevant / Off-Brand Topics.

The style of the editing guid

The style of the esiting guid fis the Chicago format where it very important to concentrate all the attentions on the evidence of the study, where the grammars of the study will be quite and simple language in arabian words, and if there are Complex understanding style is also respected in the dissertaions and the thesis of the study to be published in it. As the factor of the spelling where it will be taken in the eloquent Arabic language free from any impurities affecting it, and the images and links, where the image has the dimenssions of the 12cm×12cm in through style and it can not be a stock images or screenshot with the links must be between brackets. Finally, the using of the formate tips which will be as the dealing with Harvard Business Review.

Editorial process

The editorial process of the thesis and disertation only where the articles can not include in the process of the editoring inside the organization system, the editorial process is a process pass through the steps designed as it below:

1. The researchers of Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory submit the dissertations in the organization with the letter cover for it.
2. The reviewer make the steps of editing in three days which are:
 - Conceptual alignment editing.
 - Reliability editing.
 - Structural flow editing.
 - Use of language in arabian language editing.
 - Gramatical accuracy editing.
 - Referencing style editing.
3. Then the reviewer get the DOI identification of the dissertaion by using zenodo website.
4. The editor in Chief decide if it can send to the senior of editing
5. .send to the senior of editing and make the dissertaion will be editing.

Contributor expectations explain

The dissertation will be published in polickey on the website of the Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory organization, where will be occur after two days after the editing process, the responded from the contributors is nessary for the atudy of the dissertations. And after it take the DOI identification and publish legally the contributors can be able to publish ut as they want, and for the Who handles content updates is the contributor responsible for any updates or will the in-house editorial team manage that? They can not be able to make that.

guidelines public or easily shareable

The guidelines are easy shareable in the public ways are the zenodo DOI identifier, in facebook at the organization page, and on the website of the organization.

Reviewing paper submitted for consideration

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Publishing requirements

The requirements of the publishing are the cover letter for that is for Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory to investigate it contain that it did not publishing in any place another it. The needing also to the agreement that the dissertations and the thesis have the owner is Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory.

The messages of it

The dissertations and the thesis must contain the recommendation part which is the messages for the ideas and researches in the future build on it, and give the effects of the dissertation and the thesis of the world as it can take several levels and get it how it very important as the main question answer by it and solving the problem.

Feedback

Firstly, clearly set the answers to the main question in the dissertation, then summarize and reflect in the research process that followed, after that making of the recommendations for the future ideas and researches build on it. Fourthly, wrap up the dissertations or thesis.

The peer review process

The steps of the peer review process are firstly submit the dissertations in Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory organization, then editorial office assessment, then appraisal by the Editor-in-Chief (EIC). Fourthly, EIC Assigns an Associate Editor (AE), then make of the step is invitation to the reviewers, then response to Invitations, then review is conducted, the organization evaluate the reviews. Finally, the discussion is communicated by the Alelaimat Chemistry Laboratory organization.

The final steps

The final steps are:

- suggesting topics for special or themed issues.
- promotion within key communities.
- offering comments on published content, and suggesting future direction.
- helping to get high quality contributions.
- maintaining the ethical standards of the organization.